

**CHARACTER MIMESIS AND NAME CONFORMITY IN CHIMAMANDA
NGOZI ADICHIE'S TRILOGY**

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Abstract

Adichie's *Purple Hibiscus*, *Half of a Yellow Sun* and *Americanah* significantly demonstrate a meaningful and insightful representations of certain notable historical and contemporary characters in society. The verisimilar delineations of these memorable figures in the fictions form the veritable nexus and basis for certain vital messages which the author conveys. Indeed, her modeling of the characters of Ade Coker and Ogechi Nwankiti after the quintessential journalist Dele Giwa and environmental activist Ken Saro-Wiwa respectively, and their well known historical ordeals and eventual brutal silencing by iron-fisted and hegemonic tyrants are not just for mere ornamentation, especially in view of diverse mind-racking developments in contemporary Nigeria under supposedly democratic government. The same can be said of the characterisation of Ojukwu and Gowon with issues related to the historic Aburi Accord and the Nigerian Civil War. Other names deployed in the fictions to invoke concrete reality and achieve various artistic ends include Major Nzeogwu, Generals Buhari, Babangida, Abacha, Kudirat Abiola, Barack Obama, etc. Using New Historicism as its theoretical parameter and qualitative research methodology, the study unveils that Adichie consistently models quite a number of her major fictional characters and incidents after certain notable historical and contemporary personages and issues related to them, and that through the strategies of character mimesis and name conformity, she incorporates into her narratives a variety of textual and ideological insights from a myriad of extraneous sources in order to create knowledge, convey meanings and project her artistic visions.

Introduction

Aldous Leonard Huxley, (26 July 1894 – 22 November 1963) a renowned English philosopher and articulate writer once said, “That men do not learn very much from the lessons of history is the most important of all the lessons of history.” As indicated by the date of his death, Huxley lived long enough through the 19th century to the 20th century to have been able to reach that critical conclusion. The history of humanity is indeed replete with various exemplifications of repeated historical developments, many of which have retrogressive and tragic consequences. And when society rightly learns from tragic histories and make the necessary amendments the reverse is usually the case, hence the necessity and significance of this study. Derived from the ancient Greek word “kharakter,” character, an English word which dates from the Restoration can be said to mean a person in a narrative work of art such as a novel, play, poem, television series or film. In literary studies, characters guide readers through stories, enabling them to comprehend plots and reflect over thematic preoccupations. *Wikipedia* (2020) avers that “the study of a character requires an analysis of its relations with all of the other characters in the work. The individual status of a character is defined through the network of oppositions that it forms with the other characters” (“Character”). Also, Abrams and Harpham (2005, p.33) state that,

Characters are the persons represented in a dramatic or narrative work, who are interpreted by the reader as possessing a particular moral, intellectual and emotional qualities by inferences from what the person said and their distinctive ways of saying it - the dialogue - and from what they do - the action. The grounds in the characters’ temperaments, desires and moral nature of their speech and actions are called their motivation.

Character is so paramount in dramatic and narrative fictions that without it such a work cannot be meaningful and the author’s underlying intents cannot be achieved in any manner. In fact, a dramatic or narrative fiction without character can be said to be unrealistic. This is largely because it is through the conferment of qualities, values, actions, etc upon the characters in a literary work that thematic preoccupations crystallize and a work of art is suitably classified. The lexical item “mimesis” according to *Advanced English Dictionary* is “the imitative representation of nature and human behaviour in art and literature.” This implies the representation of the attributes of a known person or substance in a new form in an art or literary work. It suggests a sort of copying of some of the attributes of a pre-existing substance or person and representing it in a new form in order to achieve a set purpose. Character mimesis as used in the context of this study is therefore the conferment or transference of certain attributes of pre-existing historical or contemporary personalities to characters in a fictional work. Literary artists usually resort to character mimesis in order to achieve a high degree of verisimilitude which often enables the reader to connect or reconnect to historical and contemporary issues and realities. It also helps in crystallizing, humanizing and projecting the meanings the author desires to convey to a target audience. Due to such inter-connectivity of attributes between the real (original) and fictional characters, such messages usually remain vivid, lucid and memorable . Character mimesis can otherwise be referred to as role similarity. On the other hand, name conformity as applied in this study is the use of either part or full names of known historical or contemporary figures as characters in a fictional work and also conferring on the literary characters some of the attributes or actions exhibited by such figures in real life situations. In this section, character mimesis and name conformity are treated as aspects of intertextuality.

The word intertextuality is derived from the Latin “intertexto,” which means “to intermingle while weaving.” The term was first introduced in 1967 by the French semiotician Julia Kristeva in her work “Word, Dialogue and Novel.” Alfaro (1996, p.268) believes that the concept of intertextuality as initiated by Kristeva “proposes that text has a dynamic site in which relational processes and practices are the focus of analysis instead of static structures and products.” Intertextuality is the relationship that exists between texts and the way such texts either influence, differ or reflect each other. Kamalu (2012) maintains that intertextual connections can manifest in form of textual incorporation, styles, techniques, ideologies, anonymous discursive practices, codes whose origins are lost, etc.” Again, in his highlights on textual nexus, Kamalu (2012, p.120) states:

The intertextual theory...draws from the notion that no text is pure and autonomous; hence every artistic creation or text is indebted to previous one. Linguistic and literary studies recognise the relevance of precursor text in the creation and recreation of texts; hence every artistic creation or text is indebted to a precursor text.

This position was much earlier emphasized by T.S. Eliot (1964) while debunking the perception of textual autonomy in artistic creation. He states: “No poet, no artist of any art, has his complete meaning alone. His significance, his appreciation is the appreciation of his relation to the dead poets or artists. You cannot value him alone, you must set him, for contrast and comparison, among the dead.” This is to say that authors and their artistic creations always, in one way or the other, reflect previous texts or artistic orientations, a phenomenon which Bloor & Bloor (2007, p.57) popularly refers to as “standing on the shoulders of giants.” Indeed, Adichie stands on the shoulder of an African literary giant like Achebe, for instance, when she begins her first novel *Purple Hibiscus* with the statement “Things started to fall apart...” since the statement is obviously an allusion to the title of Achebe’s first and most popular novel *Things Fall Apart*, a novel whose publication contributes immensely in redefining the African narrative. Achebe himself stands on the shoulder of another giant William Butler Yeats - an Irish poet and one of the outstanding figures of 20th century literature in that the title of his famous novel is a direct repetition of a part of the third line of Yeats’ equally famous poem titled “The Second Coming” which states: “Things fall apart; the centre cannot hold.” This clearly suggests a text in dialogue with another. Hutcheon (1988, p.125) contends that “intertextual parody offers a sense of the presence of the past, but a past that can be known only from its texts, its traces – be they literary or historical.” She further argues that “to parody is not to destroy the past: in fact to parody is both to enshrine the past and to question it. And this, once again, is the postmodern paradox” (p.126).

Theoretical Perspective

New Historicism

As a critical terminology, New Historicism was first coined by the American scholar and theorist Stephen Greenblatt whose work *Renaissance Self-fashioning: From More to Shakespeare* (1980) is generally regarded as its stemma. The theory analyses a literary text with an eye on related historical developments and other issues surrounding it. Informed by the post-structuralist and reader-response theory of the 1970s as well as the rationale of feminist, Marxist and cultural critics, New Historicism can be said to be event-oriented since it interrogates whether the truth about what really happened can ever be purely or objectively ascertained. Michel Foucault, a French philosophical historian, is another notable New Historicist who assembled together incidents and phenomena from disciplines and areas hitherto perceived as unrelated and parallel. By so doing, he encouraged New Historicists to re-evaluate the boundaries of historical inquiry. Like a fellow philosopher Friedrich Nietzsche, Foucault vehemently objected to seeing history as an evolutionary process; a continuous progression from past

to present and from a cause to an effect. For him, each historical occurrence is linked to a large array or web of social, economic and political factors. Just like Karl Marx, Foucault perceived history in terms of power, but unlike Marx, Foucault believed that power is simply not an oppressive force or a manipulative tool but rather as a web of forces that generates what takes place in society.

New Historicism can be said to be an eclectic approach to the study of literature. Apart from borrowing many of its ideas from Foucault, Althusser and Marxism (particularly Raymond William's Marxist Criticism), it shares a lot of interests and ideas with feminism. These include a questioning or even subversive view of and interest in issues of social class, gender, politics, race, culture and cultural institutions. New Historicism investigates the experiences of the poor, women and the dispossessed or disenfranchised, examining their individual lives in relation to the society and power. The British equivalence of New Historicism is referred to as Cultural Materialism; a Marxist method of assessing how the discourses involved in a text embody or challenge a position of ideology. According to Peck and Coyle (1984, p.183), cultural materialism "combines studying the implications of literary texts in history, theoretical method and political commitment; and how texts relate to the particular institutions of cultural production." Indeed, it is this perception that gives New Historicism a functionalist bearing. As earlier stated, the theory remains rooted in Michel Foucault's approaches of critically examining knowledge and power and on Greenblatt's assertion that cultural discourses shape the form of history and the literature that emerges from the culture. In New Historicism, literary and non-literary texts are not ranked but are analysed on equal significance with each other, all influencing all other texts.

Issues and Discussions

In her trilogy under study, it is observed that a myriad of Adichie's fictional characters are actually modeled after certain historical and contemporary figures. The strategy as profoundly deployed by the writer in her works results to a kind of literary concretisation and crystallisation of ideas, such that an informed reader is actually often connected, subsumed and absorbed while reading any of her novels. Akachi Adimora-Ezeigbo testifies to this remarkable quality of Adichie's fictions when she describes *Purple Hibiscus* as "An original, absorbing and compelling first novel... This is a book you return to again and again; each reading draws you deeper into the vast treasures of *Purple Hibiscus*" (blurb). Femi Osofisan equally agrees in this regard that *Purple Hibiscus* is "A touching and heart-rending story...*Purple Hibiscus* captures for us the traumatic moments of... the familiar brutalities of the murderous military regimes of our recent past..." (blurb). Obviously, Osofisan identifies "... the familiar brutalities of the murderous military regimes of our recent past..." as a historical factor which endearingly connects a reader to the fiction. Name conformity and character mimesis go hand-in-hand in Adichie's fictions. The strategy enables the writer to concretise and crystallise meanings in her works as it reconnects readers to what they might have already known before concerning some incidents, issues and persons in society but are, however, presented with new literary insights which often permit a certain degree of liberty in the manipulation of resources. The literary artist is completely at liberty to do so since, in consonance with the paradigms of the literary enterprise, he is subjective in his approach and not in any way constrained by the purported objectivity of the historical discipline.

Character mimesis and name conformity in literature are not particularly new strategies. William Shakespeare, for instance, is a notable English writer known for a number of plays which scholars often prefer to categorise as historical plays not only because such plays are named after certain English monarchs whose lives and times are in one way or the other historicised or demonstrated in the plays but also for their specific and focal historical settings. Such plays include *King John*, *Richard II*, *Henry IV Part 1*, *Henry IV Part 2*, *Henry V*, *Henry VI Part 1*, *Henry VI Part 2*, *Henry VI Part III*, *Richard III* and *Henry VIII*. Nosweatshakespeare.com maintains that,

The plays normally referred to as Shakespeare history plays are the ten plays that cover English history from the twelfth to the sixteenth centuries and the 1399-1485 period in particular. Each historical play is named after, and focuses on the reigning monarch of the period. The plays dramatize five generations of medieval power struggles. For the most part, they depict the Hundred Years War with France, from Henry V to Joan of Arc, and the Wars of the Roses, between York and Lancaster. We should never forget that they are works of imagination, based very loosely on historical figures. Shakespeare was a keen reader of history and was always looking for the dramatic impact of historical characters and events as he read. Today, we tend to think of those historical figures in the way Shakespeare presented them. For example, we think of Richard III as an evil man, a kind of psychopath with a deformed body and a grudge against humanity. Historians can do whatever they like to set the record straight but Shakespeare's Richard seems stuck in our culture as the real Richard III... The history plays are enormously appealing. Not only do they give insight into the political processes of Medieval and Renaissance politics but they also offer a glimpse of life from the top to the very bottom of society - the royal court, the nobility, tavern life, brothels, beggars, everything.

The above online article as contained on the stated website has been cited at length not only because it has demonstrated that a distinguished literary artist like Shakespeare utilizes the strategy of what we have referred to as character mimesis and name conformity in this research, but also because it crystallizes and clarifies a number of postulations and assertions which we have already made from diverse findings from Adichie's novels with regards to her utilization of historical resources. And just as "Shakespeare was a keen reader of history," Adichie's intelligent deployment of these resources in her fictions equally portray her deep knowledge of notable historical developments not only in her home country Nigeria but across the globe. Indeed, she is a keen reader of history as she is also a keen user and manipulator of same in her relentless efforts to convey meanings and crystallize her artistic visions. This is why Nnyagu (2014, p.20) believes that,

Chimamanda Ngozi Adichie affirms that a true fiction should be a blend of imagination and reality when she subtly blends a lot of realities into her fiction. *Purple Hibiscus*, when studied, tends to in addition to the pleasure it offers as a fiction, also gets the audience abreast with certain sociological and historical facts.

Ade Coker is a major character in *Purple Hibiscus* and can be said to be modeled after Dele Giwa, a journalist and outspoken critic of Nigerian military government. This is to say that Ade Coker's characterisation in the novel in several ways reflects the life and time of Dele Giwa. Born on March 16, 1947 in Ife in the present day Osun State of Nigeria to a poor family who worked in the palace of Oba Adesoji Aderemi, the then Ooni of Ife, Sumonu Oladele Giwa attended Local Authority Modern School in Lagere, Ile-Ife. When his father subsequently moved to Oduduwa College, Ile-Ife as a laundry man, he gained admission to that institution. His quest for higher education propelled him further to travel to the United States of America where he earned a B.A. in English from Brooklyn College in 1977, and later enrolled for a postgraduate programme at Fordham University. Giwa was a staff of *The New York Times* for four years as a News Assistant before he relocated to Nigeria to work with *Daily Times*. Dele Giwa and other vibrant Nigerian journalists like Ray Ekpu, Dan Agbese, and Yakubu Mohammed founded *Newswatch* magazine in 1984, and the first edition was published and distributed on January 28, 1985. According to *Wikipedia* (2020), "A 1989 description of the magazine said it changed the format of print journalism in Nigeria [and] introduced bold, investigative formats in news reporting in Nigeria" ("Dele Giwa"). He was killed with a letter bomb in his Ikeja, Lagos residence on 19th October 1986 during the dictatorial regime of General Ibrahim Babangida who is widely rumoured to be the mastermind of the mail bomb. The assassination took place two days after

Giwa was quizzed by State Security Service (SSS) officials. Giwa was the quintessential founding editor of Newswatch magazine.

In *Purple Hibiscus*, Ade Coker – a character of Western Nigerian origin like Dele Giwa is the editor of *The Standard*, a newspaper owned by Kambili's father Eugene Achike. *The Standard* can be compared to Newswatch magazine in that it remains irrepressible and committed to "writing the truth" (p.5) in the face of military dictatorship and its relentless onslaughts to silence and suffocate the truth. As the quintessential lead editor of *The Standard*, Ade is openly critical of the corrupt military government, just as *Newswatch* was critical of the corruption-infested administration of General Babangida in the 80s, and consequently became a target of attack by the regime. The first time we meet Ade in the novel, we see him as an insistent and convincing character. Amnesty International has given Eugene Achike a human rights award for courageously fighting military dictatorship in the country, yet he refuses to be featured in his own newspaper, in the name of modesty. It takes only Ade's insistence and persuasion for Eugene to accept to be featured:

Papa himself would have a blank face when I looked at him, the kind of expression he had in the photo when they did the big story on him after Amnesty World gave him a human rights award. It was the only time he allowed himself to be featured in the paper. His editor, Ade Coker, had insisted on it, saying Papa deserved it, saying Papa was too modest. (*PH*, p.5)

In our next meeting with Ade, he is already arrested by the military junta and his wife is in distress; so worried for his safety as Kambili states:

A few days before my first exam, I was in my room studying, trying to focus on one word at a time, when the doorbell rang. It was Yewande Coker, the wife of Papa's editor. She was crying. 'They have taken him! They have taken him! What will I do, sir? I have three children! One is still sucking my breast! How will I raise them alone?' (*PH*, p.37)

For being a vociferous critic of the inept and corrupt military regime, Ade is arrested, detained and tortured. In this excerpt and indeed in several other parts of *Purple Hibiscus* where Ade is arrested by the military and tormented severely for his critical editorials, he is portrayed as an irrepressible character; a light and a living conscience in a dark society, a metaphor for truth and nobility. Ade is an embodiment of courage and forthrightness in a nation where falsehood, treachery, bad governance, suppression and intimidation are the order of the day. What Kambili observes of him after he is released from military detention confirms his noble attributes: "We simply saw his editorial back in *The Standard*, where he wrote about the value of freedom, about how his pen will not, could not, stop writing the truth" (p.42). Concerning Ade's alter ego, Dele Giwa, Debo Basorun, a retired major of the Nigerian Army and former Chief Press Secretary to General Ibrahim Babangida's administration states:

With endemic corruption and seemingly irredeemable graft already having a field day... the public began to dispute the president's claim of being a competent economic manager. Soon, editorial opinions started reflecting the mounting public dissatisfaction... And as soon as hungry faces began to adorn front pages, that adverse publicity signaled a further thawing of relations between the press and our government. One of the journalists who spearheaded the criticisms against the government's recklessness was the editor-in-chief of *Newswatch* magazine, Dele Giwa. "Dele" as he was fondly called had earlier served as an executive in the government-owned *Daily Times* – before co-founding that publication with Ray Ekpu, Yakubu Mohammed and

Dan Agbese – a position that brought him in contact with influential people both in and out of government. And with friends in those high places, the journalist had a near-unrestricted access to privileged information which was usually reflected in his writings. Dele was to become a favourite of the public for his satiric comments and penchant for investigating government excesses and abuse of office. His persistent demands that the ruling class submit itself for public accountability demonstrated the courage behind a congenial demeanour. ...Being no stranger to harassment as a guest of the security agencies, Dele showed up at my office one day to ask for my intervention... His dirt-digging (investigative journalism) talents soon became legendary. At a stage, he was reported to be planning to chronicle the sordid practices of several highly placed government officials in his journal. His weekly sermons which also targeted human rights violations was however not amusing to those benefiting from the decay. Apparently, Dele's attempt to mobilise an articulate citizenry in the fight to eradicate corruption and enshrine the inviolability of the people's rights had cost him his life. The news of the assassination spread like an inferno, leading to a huge outrage from Nigerians of different walks of life. (Basorun, 2013, p.186-188)

Before the assassination of Ade Coker under a military dictatorship as it was the case with Dele Giwa under the brutal dictatorship of General Babangida in 1986, Adichie has also portrayed Ade as a lively personality who knows how to maintain a cordial relationship with his boss and his family. His visit to Eugene, his boss, and his family in their ancestral home, Abba, goes a long way in showcasing the value he places on good relationship. He is a man who knows how to unwind and relate well with his immediate family and that of others as Kambili states:

Jaja and I were upstairs unpacking when Mama came in and said, "Ade Coker came by with his family to wish us a Merry Christmas. They are on their way to Lagos. Come downstairs and greet them." Ade was a small, round, laughing man. He looked like a stuffed doll, and because he was always smiling, the deep dimples in his pillowy cheeks looked like permanent fixtures, as though someone had sunk a stick into his cheeks. He was throwing his baby, a perfectly round copy of himself, in the air when we came in. His little daughter was standing close to him, asking him to throw her in the air, too. (PH, 56-57)

All through his stay in Eugene's house in Abba during that visit, Ade's attitude and disposition portray him as a joyful and playful person, and one who shows concern and care for the feelings of others. He asks Jaja and Kambili a number of playful questions about themselves and their hometown. It is during that interaction that Ade observes that Jaja and Kambili "are always so quiet" (p.57), and Eugene is quick to answer that "they are not like those loud children people are raising these days, with no home training and no fear of God." Here we see Ade the critically observant man; the same way he observes the diverse absurdities in the nation under an authoritarian regime spear-headed by the character Big Oga, otherwise referred to as the Head of State. The quietness of Jaja and Kambili is, however, due to the intimidating tendencies of their dictatorial father; the same manner Big Oga is relentlessly trying to quieten the entire nation with brute force.

When Jaja and Kambili visit Nsukka for the first time, a discussion comes up in Auntie Ifeoma's house during which Father Amadi says, "*The Standard* is the only paper that dares to tell the truth these days" (p.136), Auntie Ifeoma responds, "And he has a brilliant editor, Ade Coker." People's perception of *The Standard* as "the only paper that dares to tell the truth these days" is similar to the reputation of *Newswatch* magazine at the time Dele Giwa served as its editor-in-chief. Again, Basorun (2013, p.186-187) testifies to this when he writes:

Dele was to become a favourite of the public for his satiric comments and penchant for investigating government excesses... Why was Dele such a darling? To a people that had been continuously subjected to grinding poverty in a country drifting on the sea of malaise, his crusade was somewhat of unique social obligation. His dirt-digging (investigative journalism) soon became legendary.

Again, just like Ade Coker in Adichie's *Purple Hibiscus*, Basorun (2013, p.187) equally notes that Dele Giwa "...was subjected to periodic detention without charges and physically assaulted. But despite the intimidation, Dele refused to back down from what to him seemed a patriotic duty."

In *Purple Hibiscus*, the good reputation of *The Standard* newspaper is not only attributed to Eugene's focused nature but also to Ade's brilliance and doggedness. Father Amadi's assertion that "*The Standard* is the only paper that dares to tell the truth these days" as well as Aunty Ifeoma's prompt response that "...he has a brilliant editor, Ade Coker" (p.136) portray Ade as an articulate and intelligent personality who immensely contributes to the good image of the establishment that employs him. Ade is a stickler to principles and journalistic ethics; a man who will not succumb to any form of bribery, not even from the Head of State. A lover and stickler to truth, Ade would not accept a cover up nor allow anyone to influence him to under-report burning issues that affect the nation no matter how risky the situation might appear to be. Kambili says of Ade: "He was saying that Big Oga's assistant – Ade Coker referred to the Head of State as Big Oga even in his editorials - had called to say that Big Oga was willing to give him an exclusive interview" (p.196). But Ade understands that the "exclusive interview" Big Oga has suddenly proposed and even sends his personal assistant to notify him of, is intended to be used to "bribe" him. It is an interview the Head of State wants to use to soften Ade the tough editor-in-chief, in order to make him to soft-pedal or be more economical with the truth on issues concerning Nwankiti Ogechi – a human rights and pro-democracy activist who is wasted by Big Oga's tyrannical regime. So Ade retorts: "But they want me to cancel the Nwankiti Ogechi story. Imagine the stupid man, he said they knew some useless people had told me stories that I planned to use in my piece and that the stories were lies" (*PH*, p.196). Nwankiti Ogechi at first goes missing and there are speculations about his whereabouts. One of the speculations which later turned out to be true is that government soldiers shot him in Minna and then burned his body with acid. This is the true situation which the Head of State tries relentlessly to conceal at the moment, especially in view of the fact that "the Commonwealth Nations were meeting." So "the Big people in Abuja don't want the story to be out now" (p.196). But Ade says "No way!" He further reveals the reason for his refusal: "They don't want Nwankiti Ogechi to become an issue now. Simple! And you know what it means; it means they have wasted him! Which one is for Big Oga to try and bribe me with an interview? I ask you, eh, which one is that?" (p.197). Eventually, it is confirmed that "Soldiers shot Nwankiti Ogechi in a bush in Minna. And then they poured acid on his body to melt his flesh off his bones, to kill him even when he was already dead" (p.1988).

The murder of Nwankiti Ogechi causes Nigeria to be suspended from the Commonwealth Nations. Other international sanctions slammed against the country for human rights abuses and dictatorship are also swiftly tightened as a result. By linking the death of Nwankiti Ogechi to the despotic activities of the Head of State, and stating that Ogechi's body is burned with acid after wasting him and also noting that the incident coincided with the period the Commonwealth Nations were meeting, Adichie can be said to be drawing a parallel to the killing of Ken Saro-Wiwa, a renowned author and environmental activist. Saro-Wiwa led a movement to protect Ogoniland in Nigeria's oil-rich Niger Delta region from environmental degradation orchestrated by foreign petroleum companies extracting oil and exploiting the people of the area. He was arrested during his protests by the military government of General Sani Abacha and tried. In 1995, he was executed by hanging and his body was burned with acid. And it was on account of that occurrence that Nigeria was suspended from the

Commonwealth of Nations for over three years due to the international outrage over his gruesome execution. Art, again, appears to mimic reality in the novel when a few years after the death of the fictional Ogechi, it is stated that the Head of State has died, rumoured to involve a prostitute: “After the Head of State died months ago – they say he died atop a prostitute, foaming at the mouth and jerking” (p.289). This parallels the death of General Sani Abacha on June 8, 1998, rumoured to involve a conspiracy through a prostitute. Abacha was widely rumoured to have eaten a poisoned apple given to him at bed by a pretty prostitute.

While Ade fights for justice in the government-sponsored assassination of Nwankiti Ogechi, he does not know that the same fate is awaiting him. Eventually, Ade the courageous, irrepressible and uncompromising editor of *The Standard* is killed. Even the weather and nature are angry as Kambili narrates:

It rained heavily the day Ade Coker died, a strange, furious rain in the middle of the harmattan. Ade Coker was at breakfast with his family when a courier delivered a package everybody would have known was from the Head of State even if his wife Yawande had not said that Ade Coker looked at the envelope and said, “It has the State House Seal” before he opened it. (p.202)

Ade is killed with a letter bomb presumably sent from the State House. The government, by all means, wants him out of the way because he is an outspoken critic of their dictatorial and cruel regime. It has been earlier stated that Adichie models the character of Ade Coker after Dele Giwa, a veteran journalist and outspoken critic of Nigerian military government. Like Ade Coker, Giwa was killed with a mail bomb in 1986. Through these obvious mimicry of historical realities, Adichie resonates real political events. In his “Fiction as a Blend of Facts and Imagination in Chimamanda Ngozi Adichie’s *Purple Hibiscus*,” Nnyagu (2014, p.22-24) in enunciating issues that relate to the characters of Big Oga, Ade Coker and Nwankiti Ogechi states:

Historical facts about...Nigeria...are mirrored by Adichie. One reading *Purple Hibiscus* needs not crack one's brain much trying to decode the history mirrored by the author. Ade Coker the editor in the fiction, is the historical Dele Giwa who was killed via letter bomb. On several occasions, the fictional Ade Coker was arrested for saying the truth about the nation, and her governance in *The Standard* which he is the editor. The true pictures of the murders of Ken Saro-Wiwa and Dele Giwa are aptly mirrored by Adichie. Historical Ken Saro-Wiwa is symbolized by the fictional character Nwankiti Ogechi... The military Heads of State never wanted anybody to see the truth about their dictatorship, and anybody who dared reveal the fact would face his fate. The death of Dele Giwa is no longer news in Nigeria. Even the afro beat musician, Fela sang a satirical song about the murder. Adichie pathetically fictionalizes the fact about the killing and perpetual horror witnessed in Nigeria during the military rules under Generals Sani Abacha and Ibrahim Babangida... through the invented character, we see the historical reality of the killing of Dele Giwa... *Purple Hibiscus* mirrors how corrupt Nigeria was during the military regime, precisely during Abacha and Babangida regimes. Adichie succinctly paints a true picture of the ills of the Heads of State and how they dared not spare anybody who dared to criticize their corrupt and autocratic administration. Journalists were afraid to report facts except very few who, in spite of all odds, determine never to sit on the fence. Ade Coker is a paradigm of such determined journalists as mirrored by Adichie. Of course, the fate of such determined journalists in a corrupt society like Nigeria is made obvious by Adichie through the murder of Ade Coker.

In *Half of a Yellow Sun*, Adichie in her “Author’s Note” states that,

While some of the characters are based on actual persons, their portrayals are fictitious...Christopher Okigbo's own life and *Labyrinths* inspired the character of Okeoma; while Alexander Madiebo's *The Nigerian Revolution and the Biafran War* was central to the character of Colonel Madu. (p.433)

This statement simply implies that Adichie models the characters of Okeoma and Colonel Madu after the historical characters Christopher Okigbo and Alexander Madiebo. In other words, the fictional characters of Okeoma and Colonel Madu in *Half of a Yellow Sun* are imitations of the historical characters of Christopher Okigbo and Alexander Madiebo. This is the thrust of character mimesis in the context of this discourse. Christopher Ifekandu Okigbo, a quintessential Nigerian poet of Igbo extraction, was born on August 16, 1932 in Ojoto town in the present day Anambra State of Nigeria. His father taught in Catholic Missionary Schools during the days of British colonial administration in the country, thereby making the young Christopher to move from station to station as his father was transferred. Okigbo attended and graduated from Government College Umuahia in the present day Abia State before gaining admission to the University College, Ibadan where he originally wanted to study Medicine but, however, switched over to classics in his second year. *Wikipedia* notes that “In College, he... earned a reputation as a gifted pianist, accompanying Wole Soyinka in his first public appearance as a singer” (“Christopher Okigbo”). When he graduated in 1956, he worked in a number of establishments and institutions which included: Nigerian Tobacco Company, United Africa Company, Fiditi Grammar School – where he taught Latin, and then as Assistant Librarian at the University of Nigeria, Nsukka where he was, alongside other intellectuals, instrumental in founding the African Authors Association. It was during those days that he started publishing some of his works in various journals, notably *Black Orpheus*. Okigbo left Nsukka in 1964 to become the West African representative of Cambridge University Press at Ibadan – a position that gave him the opportunity to often travel to the United Kingdom. While at Ibadan at the period, he became actively involved with the Mbari Literary Club and completed and published some of his works like *Limits* (1964), *Silences* (1962-65), *Lament of the Masks* (1964), *Dance of the Painted Maidens* (1964) and his evocative and prophetic *Path of Thunder* which was published posthumously in 1971 alongside his *Labyrinths*.

At the outbreak of diverse hostilities in Nigeria in 1967, Okigbo left Ibadan and relocated to the Eastern Region where he collaborated with Chinua Achebe at Enugu to establish the Citadel Press. With the declaration of the Sovereign State of Biafra on May 30, 1967, he promptly joined the Biafran Army as a volunteer – a field-commissioned major. The sun suddenly set for Okigbo in 1967 when he was wasted at the Nsukka Sector of the Civil War. The same University town where he had earlier worked as an Assistant Librarian and found his voice as a distinguished poet, he indeed ended up defending it with his own blood.

Adichie mirrors the life and time of Okigbo through the character of Okeoma in several ways. The first time we meet Okeoma in *Half of a Yellow Sun*, he is introduced as one of “the regular guests”(p.18) at Odenigbo's house at the staff quarters of the University of Nigeria Nsukka. The narrator introduces Okeoma as the third person in a fairly long list of regular guests, after Dr Patel “the Indian man who drank Golden Guinea beer mixed with Coke. Master called him Doc,” and the “skinny Professor Ezeka, with a voice so hoarse he sounded as if he spoke in whispers” (p.18). Then in Okeoma’s case, the narrator states:

There was Okeoma, who came most often and stayed the longest. He looked younger than the others guests, always wore a pair of shorts, and had bushy hair with a parting at the side that stood higher than Master's. It looked rough and tangled, unlike Master's as

if Okeoma did not like to comb it. Okeoma drank Fanta. He read his poetry aloud on some evenings, holding a sheaf of papers, and Ugwu would look through the kitchen door to see all the guests watching him, their faces half frozen, as if they did not dare breathe. Afterwards, Master would clap and say, in his loud voice, “The voice of our generation!” and the clapping would go on until Okeoma said sharply, “That’s enough!”(p.18-19)

Indeed, Okigbo was one of the poetic voices of his generation since again, according to *Wikipedia*, he was awarded “the first prize in African poetry... at the 1966 World Festival of Negro Arts in Dakar.” He, however, rejected the prize on the ground that “there is no such thing as a Negro or black poet.” Adichie also draws a parallel from Okigbo’s appearance when she describes that Okeoma “...looked younger...had bushy hair...” Okigbo fell in battle at the age of 34 – a promising, budding and burgeoning poet and activist. Just like Okigbo, Okeoma dies fighting with the secessionist Biafran Army in a determined effort to retake Umuahia, the Biafran capital when it falls into the hands of federal troops, although in historical reality, Okigbo died at the Nsukka Sector. The shock of a wasted potential and talent sticks to one's heart when the omniscient narrator states:

Then, one evening, it rained, a flinty, blustery rain, a strange shower in the dry season, and perhaps it was why Odenigbo did not go to the bar. And it was the evening that Dr Nwala came to tell them that Okeoma had been killed. Lightning flashed across the sky and thunder rumbled...Dr Nwala came in, water dripping down his face. He was thinner and lankier than she remembered and looked as though he would break in two if he sat down abruptly. He did not sit down. He did not waste time with greetings. He had raised his loose shirt away from his body, was rapidly flipping it to get the water off when he said, 'Okeoma has gone, O jebego. They were on a mission to retake Umuahia when it happened. I saw him last month, and he told me he was writing some poems and Olanna was his muse, and if anything happened to him I should make sure the poems went to her. (*Half*, p.391)

It can be said that a number of major characters modeled after actual historical figures in Adichie’s fictions (Ogechi Nwankiti – Ken Saro-Wiwa, Ade Coker – Dele Giwa, and Okeoma - Christopher Okigbo) largely suffer similar fate like their respective alter ego. They are all wasted on the altar of strife and politicking. While Nwankiti Ogechi’s deceased body is burned with concentrated acid as it was the case with Ken Saro-Wiwa in 1995, Ade Coker is wasted with a mail bomb “rumoured” to have been sent from the State House as it was the situation with Dele Giwa in 1986; then Okeoma the talented poet is slain at the battlefield during the Nigerian Civil War as it was the case of Christopher Okigbo in 1967. Adichie uses these verisimilar circumstances of fate to re-echo political realities and to demonstrate that her inspirations to fictionalize are not, after all, drawn from a vacuum.

In the case of the character of Colonel Madu in *Half of a Yellow Sun*, Adichie’s prompt admittance that “...Alexander Madiebo's *The Nigerian Revolution and the Biafran War* was central to the character of Colonel Madu” (p.434) is a crystal truth even to a blind man who perhaps had the opportunity of having the work read to him. Madiebo’s work although a historical account of the stated events can as well be called his autobiography which chronicles, in monumental details, a myriad of landmark events in his life as a commissioned Nigerian military officer, and later the General Officer Commanding (GOC) the Biafran Army from 1967 to the end of the war in 1970. Colonel Madu's miraculous and narrow escape from the pogroms in Northern Nigeria after the successful July counter coup is clearly a re-enactment of Lieutenant Colonel Alexander Madiebo’s amazing escape from death in Kaduna as one of the targeted Igbo officers. Until the counter coup which Adichie also historicised,

Madiebo was the Commander of Nigerian Army Artillery Corps based in Kaduna. Again, Adichie's Colonel Madu also commands Biafran Army as Madiebo did during that historical crisis.

Another major character in *Half of a Yellow Sun* which reflects and re-echoes a significant historical figure is that of Major Nzeogwu. In this case, Adichie adopts the strategy of name conformity and character mimesis simultaneously. Major Chukwuma Kaduna Nzeogwu popularly called Major Nzeogwu, just as Adichie does in her novel, was the protagonist of Nigerian military politics. He does not need any introduction whatsoever in the Nigerian military, political and historical circles. The mention of his name within these circles does not in any way sound ambiguous, especially to an educated and informed Nigerian. Born on February 26, 1937 in Kaduna, Patrick Chukwuma Kaduna Nzeogwu attended Saint Joseph's Catholic Primary School, Kaduna for his elementary education and Saint John's College for his secondary education. He enlisted as an officer-cadet in the Nigerian regiment of the West African Frontier Force in March, 1957 before proceeding on a six-month preliminary training in the Gold Coast, now Ghana. By October 1957, he completed his training and then proceeded to the Royal Military Academy, the British highbrow officer factory in Sandhurst where he was commissioned as an infantry officer in 1959. He subsequently received a platoon officer's training in Hythe and a platoon commander's course in Warminster. Nzeogwu returned to Nigeria in May 1960 and was deployed to the 1st Battalion in Enugu where Major J.T.U. Aguiyi-Ironsi was the second-in-command under a British officer. He was subsequently posted to the 5th Battalion in Kaduna where he met and became friends with Olusegun Obasanjo.

He became a training officer at the Nigerian Army Training Depot, Zaria for about 6 months, after serving in the peace keeping operation in the Congo in 1961 alongside his friend Olusegun Obasanjo. Then he was deployed to Lagos where he became the first indigenous Nigerian military officer to head the military intelligence of the Nigerian Army at the Army Headquarters. He served in that capacity from November 1962 to 1964. It was in his service in that capacity that he was significantly involved in the investigations for treasonable felony of Chief Obafemi Awolowo and other members of the Action Group political party. As it is the nature of military service, he was subsequently posted, again, to Kaduna where he became Chief Instructor at the Nigerian Military Training College. As Chief Instructor, Nzeogwu initiated "Operation Damisa" (Lion Hunt) - a two-day night exercise involving soldiers contributed from various army units in Kaduna, and then used it as a platform to execute the first military coup in Nigeria in the early hours of 15th January, 1966. According to Obasanjo (1987, p.86),

Under the pretext of a military exercise, the troops of the Nigerian Military Training College where Chukwuma was chief instructor, had been called out with troops of all other units in Kaduna, and the brigade headquarters has approved the exercise without suspecting anything. Exercise 'Damisa' or 'Lion Hunt' turned out to be a coup, designed to hunt down the political and military leaders. At dawn on 15th January 1966, Kaduna woke up to the muted shock of a perfectly successful coup in the regional capital.

The character of Major Nzeogwu in Adichie's *Half of a Yellow Sun* is brought into the fiction from the very point the first military coup is announced in Nigeria, signaling the demise of the First Republic. This coup which serves as one of the precursors of the major conflict in the novel – the Nigerian Civil War – like the historical January 1966 coup also announced by the historical character of Major Nzeogwu, equally results to the death of some of the same national political figures namely: the premier of Northern Nigeria, the Finance Minister, Prime Minister Balewa among others (*Half*, p.123-124). Even the statement that "The BBC is calling it an Igbo coup" (*Half*, p.124) equally re-echoes historical reality because in actuality, Major Nzeogwu's coup of 1966 was promptly tagged an Igbo coup largely because majority of the officers involved in the planning were of Igbo extraction. In

addition, according to a character Adichie simply identifies as “Chin-chin-eating guests” at Odenigbo’s house at Nsukka, “...they have a point. It was mostly Northerners who were killed” (*Half*, p.123) in contrast to their Southern military and political counterparts. Again, the coup was executed and announced by Major Nzeogwu – an officer of Igbo descent who hailed from Okpanam Town, near Asaba – a town of the Anioma people in the present day Delta State. Adichie unambiguously demonstrates that the character of Major Nzeogwu is indeed modeled after the historical Nigerian Major Nzeogwu when she reproduced verbatim (p.123-124) the coup speech delivered to a bewildered nation in the early hours of January 15, 1966 by the same historical character. In doing this, Adichie seemed to have melted or welded history and arts together in the fiction. Thus historical production and artistic production seemed to have come together in a harmonious, meaningful union. Again, the initial euphoria that greeted the historical coup announcement of Major Nzeogwu equally greets the coup represented in Adichie’s fiction for soon after the coup is announced on the radio, Odenigbo’s guests erupt in jubilation. The narrator notes that “their voices were urgent and excited, each person barely waiting for the last to finish speaking” (*Half*, p.124). “This is the end of corruption! This is what we have needed to happen since that general strike,” one guest said.

“Those majors are true heroes!” Okeoma said and raised an alarm. Then it is again noted that “there was excitement in their voices even when they talked about the people who were killed” (*Half*, p.125). Odenigbo caps up the excitement of the guests in his house at the announcement of the coup when he says, “If we had more men like Major Nzeogwu in this country, we would not be where we are today” (*Half*, p.125). Adichie uses these expressions as stated by her characters to capture the historical mood and expressions of Nigerians at the receipt of the news of Major Nzeogwu’s historical coup. The euphoria was, however, short-lived when, as several issues and perspectives of the coup unfolded, it was gathered that the Northern and Western Regions of the country suffered more casualties with the assassinations of a number of their key political office holders and military personnel than the Eastern Region. And, again, just as in historical reality, Nzeogwu’s coup catalysed the greatest conflict in the novel – the Nigerian Civil War.

Ojukwu and Gowon are also notable characters in *Half of a Yellow Sun*. This is a typical exemplification of name conformity - a literary strategy which the author adopts in order to reinforce verisimilitude and realism in her work. In the novel, Ojukwu and Gowon play the most significant political and administrative roles in that both men are Heads of State of the secessionist Biafra and the Federal Nigeria respectively, just as in historical reality. At the heat of the incessant massacres of Igbo people soon after the July counter coup, Aburi is the meeting point where both leaders discuss the need to end all hostilities and consequently reach an agreement known as the, Aburi Accord. Adichie fictionalizes these historical realities when she narrates:

Aburi came up often in their conversations: Okeoma would say that Gowon should have followed the agreement he and Ojukwu signed in Aburi, or Professor Ezeka would say that Gowon’s renegeing after Aburi meant that he did not wish the Igbo well, or Odenigbo would proclaim, “On Aburi we stand.” (*Half*, p.159)

Okeoma goes on to state the content of the Aburi Accord when in reference to the character of Gowon he says, “He agreed to confederation at Aburi, and now he wants one Nigeria with a unitary government, but a unitary government was the very reason that he and his people killed Igbo officers” (*Half*, p.159). Like Okeoma, many Easterners even in historical and contemporary reality believe that confederation was at the centre of the historical Aburi Accord and not a unitary governmental system. *Advanced English Dictionary* defines the lexical item confederation as:

1. The state of being allied or confederated

2. A union of political organizations
3. The act of forming an alliance or confederation

One of the major implications of confederation as a lexical item and a political term is having a relatively weak centre and strong regions usually referred to as the confederating units. Such units by design are legally or constitutionally allowed to have a measure of control over the resources emanating from their lands, and contribute an agreed quota for the smooth running and functionality of the centre. This, of course, is still the cause of several agitations from diverse regions of the country till today. The characterisation of Ojukwu and Gowon in the novel really conform to the historical roles played by Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu and Yakubu Gowon in the thirty-months bloody Nigerian Civil War which lasted between June 6, 1967 and January 15, 1970.

The breakdown of the Aburi Accord results to the historic declaration of the State of Biafra on May 29, 1967 in the city of Enugu in Eastern Nigeria. Adichie fictionalizes this significant declaration using the same character Ojukwu (*Half*, p.161-162). And as it is the case with the historical Major Nzeogwu's coup speech of January 15, 1966, the historical Ojukwu's declaration of the Sovereign State of Biafra is intertextualized by Adichie in *Half of a Yellow Sun* in that the exact words, sentences, punctuation, phrases and paragraphs used by the historical Ojukwu in that significant declaration are equally used by the fictional Ojukwu. Here, again, art and historical reality are melted together in a harmonious union.

In *Americanah*, Adichie adds a new dimension to her strategy of character mimesis and name conformity as previously utilized in her first two novels. In *Purple Hibiscus*, historical characters like Dele Giwa, Babangida/Abacha and Ken Saro-Wiwa are fictionalized as Ade Coker, Big Oga/Head of State and Nwankiti Ogechi respectively, for instance. This conforms to the earlier pattern of characterising and fictionalizing historical figures as seen in the novels of first generation Nigerian writers like Chinua Achebe (*A Man of the People*, *Anthills of the Savannah*), Chukwuemeka Ike (*Sunset at Dawn*) etc, in that she uses entirely fictitious names to represent such historical figures. In *Half of a Yellow Sun*, she gains a measure of boldness and uses both fictitious names as well as real historical surnames which easily invoke the full names of such historical figures as well as their actions and inactions in history. In *Americanah*, however, Adichie becomes daring and overt on the issue of character mimesis and name conformity in that in quite a number of such historical and contemporary personages she alludes to or represents in the fiction, she uses either their real surnames or their full names. Such characters in *Americanah* include: Obasanjo, Generals Buhari, Babangida, Abacha, Princess Diana, Barack Obama, Hillary Clinton, Kudirat Abiola and even the notorious Nigerian armed robber Lawrence Anini. This seems to be a significant feature of third generation Nigerian/African literary creation of which Adichie's novels can be categorized. This is as opposed to the conservativeness demonstrated in fictionalizing such historical personages as seen in the fictions of first generation writers as earlier stated. It is, however, noteworthy that apart from the characters of Barack Obama and Hillary Clinton which Adichie gives a comparably elaborate characterisations, she largely alludes to the rest of the historical and contemporary figures in the fiction. This is also precisely the case with the four Nigerian leaders that appear in the novel, namely Obasanjo, Generals Buhari, Babangida and Abacha. Although she does not give them much discursive space, her allusions to and portrayals of their roles in history are succinct and unambiguous. For instance, the roles of Generals Abacha, Babangida and Obasanjo in Nigeria's sociopolitical and economic history crystallize as they are invoked by a character identified as Chief when he says:

Remember those big Bankers during Abacha's government? They thought they owned this country, and the next thing they knew, they were in prison. Look at the pauper who

could not pay his house rent before, then Babangida gave him an oil well, and now he has a private jet! ... I was Babangida's friend. I was Abacha's friend. Now that the military has gone, Obasanjo is my friend. Do you know why? They said the National Farm Support Corporation is bankrupt and they're going to privatize it. (*Americanah*, p.24-26)

In historical reality, General Abacha is associated with the Failed Banks Tribunal which indeed gave long prison sentences to a number of Chief Executive Officers of some failed banks in 1997 for corruption and mismanagement of public funds, although, ironically, he himself was stinking corrupt and also mismanaged the Nigerian estate. General Babangida's settlement philosophy is highlighted while President Obasanjo's questionable privatization programme is foregrounded. She equally alludes to General Buhari's austerity measures and high-handedness in leadership when she states that,

...General Buhari's soldiers were flogging adults in the streets, lecturers were striking for better pay...when General Buhari's government stopped giving essential commodities, and she no longer came home with free tins of milk, she had begun to grind soya beans at home to make milk. (*Americanah*, p.232, 281)

She makes a specific reference to the gruesome assassination of Alhaja Kudirat Abiola on June 4, 1996 when the character of Bartholomew says, "Kudirat's death will not be in vain, it will only galvanise the democratic movement in a way that even her life did not!"(p.116), as well as Lawrence Anini's notoriety in the 1980s in Nigeria when she states that "Ifemelu had watched the firing squad that killed Lawrence Anini, fascinated by the mythologies around his armed robberies..." (p.148).

Adichie also fictionalizes the characters of Barack Obama and Hillary Clinton largely and primarily in connection with America's Presidential election of 2008 and the engaging hot debate centering on race and racism, Obama being the first black man to get to that remarkable point of clinching the Democratic presidential ticket that same year and eventually winning the presidential election. The fictionalization of Barack Obama and Hillary Clinton in *Americanah* is similar to that of Major Nzeogwu, Ojukwu and Gowon, among others, in *Half of a Yellow Sun* in that apart from using the real names of such historical and contemporary characters and characterizing them in conformity with some of their actual historical roles, the characters are all given wide discursive spaces in contrast to the marginal discursive spaces and allusions made to other similar historical characters. These characters mentioned by their real names in the fictions all play significant, turning-point roles in their respective nations. This is to say that their roles in the fictions largely mimic their roles in reality. Adichie presents an excerpt of President Barack Obama's historic declaration speech of December 10, 2007, to contest for the office of the president of the United States of America when she states:

And that is why, in the shadow of the Old State Capitol, where Lincoln once called on a divided house to stand together, where common hopes and common dreams still live, I stand before you today to announce my candidacy for president of the United States of America. (*Americanah*, p.328)

This speech is comparable to the excerpts of the historic speeches in *Half of a Yellow Sun* as attributed to the characters of Major Nzeogwu (p.123) and Ojukwu (p.161) in that both speeches significantly and dramatically change the course of history in their respective nations. The immediate consequence of Major Nzeogwu's speech is the death of Nigeria's First Republic while that of Ojukwu signals the commencement of the Nigerian Civil War. It is only that of Barack Obama that can be said to have monumental positive outcomes in the history of his nation in that the speech elicits enduring hope and joy in the novel as it did in historical reality. Obama is a jinx breaker whose story continues

to inspire readers with optimism across the globe. His story as the first black President of the United States has also significantly altered the African American narrative in that country.

There is also a sort of characterization and contextualization of Hillary Clinton and the enormous good will that greeted and followed her gigantic aspiration to become the first female president of the United States of America, especially among female characters who see the possibility of her victory as victory for women globally, in view of the contestations of feminism against patriarchy. This is perhaps one of the reasons why although Ifemelu (a female character) shares the same black identity with Obama, she initially pitches her tent with Hillary Clinton when she says, “I like Hillary Clinton. I don't really know anything about this Obama guy” (p.329). The narrator, however, states some of the reasons why Ifemelu likes Hillary Clinton initially:

At first, even though she wished America would elect a black man as president, she thought it impossible, and she could not imagine Obama as president of the United States; he seemed too light, too skinny, a man who would be blown away by the wind. Hillary Clinton was sturdier. Ifemelu liked to watch Clinton on television, in her square trouser suits, her face a mask of resolve, her prettiness disguised, because that was the only way to convince the world that she was able. Ifemelu liked her. She wished her victory, willed good fortune her way... (*Americanah*, p.352)

Clinton's female advantage is also highlighted when Puala says, “Isn't it funny how they say 'blacks want Obama' and 'women want Hillary'...” (p.355). Then Nathan adds that “...Clinton is benefiting because she's a white woman...” (p.355). Nathan goes further to say,

If Clinton were a black woman, her star would not have shined as brightly. If Obama were a white man, his star might or might not shine so brightly, because some white men have become president who had no business being president, but that doesn't change the fact that Obama doesn't have a lot of experience and people are excited by the idea of a black candidate who has a real chance. (*Americanah*, p.356)

In reference to the characters of Ifemelu and Blaine, when they eventually staunchly queue up with others in absolute support for Obama's presidential candidacy, the narrator observes that, “They believed. They truly believed. It often came to her as a sweet shock, the knowledge that there were so many people in the world who felt exactly as she and Blaine about Barack Obama” (p.357).

CONCLUSION

Adichie effectively uses the strategies of character mimesis and name conformity to meaningfully fictionalize and historicise significant historical figures and occurrences in her novels in order to invoke realism and inspire a level of socio-historical consciousness that would enable society to be constantly reminded of the past from which veritable lessons must be learnt in order to collectively build a better future. The novels demonstrate a high degree of intertextuality which is a crystallizing evidence that they are neither derived from nor exist in a vacuum. This shows that it is largely as part of prior discourses that they derive their meanings and significance. Adichie also deploys these illuminating strategies to achieve an optimal degree of verisimilitude and realism in her focal texts. These serve the purpose of connecting and reconnecting the fictions to the sensibilities of various categories of readers across the globe. While she mainly alludes to a variety of historical figures in *Americanah*, she deeply and extensively contextualizes and characterizes them in *Purple Hibiscus* and *Half of a Yellow Sun*.

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